

NAVIGATING FILE FORMATS IN DIGITAL PRESERVATION

TIFFs, JPEGs, EPUBs, and PDFs in Practice

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AGENDA

- INTRODUCTION
- SIGNIFICANCE OF FILE FORMATS
- KEY FORMATS
- TOOLS
- OUR JOURNEY
- Q & A

**WHY
FILE FORMAT
CHOICE MATTERS**

KEY REASONS FILE FORMAT MATTERS

Technological Obsolescence

Proprietary or outdated formats may no longer be supported by modern software, risking loss of critical records.

Vendor Lock -in

Proprietary formats make switching providers difficult, resulting in long - term dependency and reduced flexibility.

Compliance and Legal Risks

Using unsustainable formats can make compliance difficult, with potential legal consequences or fines.

Search and Retrieval Difficulties

Poorly structured formats are hard to index and search, making document location inefficient and unreliable.

Costly Data Migrations

Migrating data in non - standard formats is expensive, time - consuming, and prone to data loss.

COMMON CHALLENGES

OBSOLESCENCE

Obsolescence is when a file format becomes *outdated or unsupported over time.*

- Older formats can lose software support
- Planned obsolescence pushes upgrades
- Open-source support may fade
- Some formats simply stop being supported

PROLIFERATION

Proliferation is when there are *too many different file formats or versions* to manage effectively.

- Too many formats create management issues
- Multiple versions of the same format (e.g. PDFs, Word)
- Hard to track, maintain, and access

HOW TO ADDRESS IT

- Migrate to preferred formats
- Use emulation where needed
- Normalise formats
- Make deliberate, long term format choices

KEY CONSIDERATIONS

- 1 MATCH FORMAT TO CONTENT
AND COLLECTION NEEDS
- 2 IDENTIFY ESSENTIAL
PROPERTIES
- 3 PREFER OPEN,
WELL-DOCUMENTED FORMATS
- 4 CONSIDER COMMUNITY
ADOPTION AND SUPPORT

LOSSLESS

LOSSLESS FORMATS

- Preserve all original data without quality loss.
- Ideal for archival masters and long-term preservation.

Example: TIFF for high-resolution image storage

LOSSY

LOSSY FORMATS

- Compress data by sacrificing some quality.
- Better suited for access copies and distribution where file size matters.

Example: JPEG for online viewing and delivery

LOSSLESS VS LOSSY

THE IMPORTANCE OF FILE FORMAT IDENTIFICATION

Good identification enables

- Predict future accessibility.
- Flag potentially obsolete or unsupported formats.
- Reduce the risk of data loss.
- Inform preservation actions like migration or normalisation

Why file extensions aren't enough

- Extensions can be wrong or misleading.
- Different formats can share the same extension but behave differently.
- Some files have no extension at all

Tools for identification

- DROID- automated format identification
- PRONOM technical format registry

Maintained by The National Archives (UK), widely used internationally

KEY FORMATS

- ❑ TIFFs
- ❑ JPEG
- ❑ PDF
- ❑ EPUB

TIFFs

OVERVIEW

- Tagged Image File Format
.tif or .tiff file extension
- Released 1986 (current version 6.0 since 1992)
- Lossless image format
- Supports multicolour spaces and bit depth up to 64
- Can store multiple pages/layers in one file

STRENGTHS

- Ideal for long term preservation masters
- Stable and well documented (non proprietary)
- Strong metadata support
- High image quality retained over time

LIMITATIONS

- Large file sizes require significant storage
- Not ideal for access or quick loading
- Limited browser and system support
- Long transfer time

JPEGs

OVERVIEW

- Created by the Joint Photographic Experts Group in 1992
- File extension can be .jpg / .jpeg
- Supports RGB and CMYK colourspaces
- Compressed, lossy raster format

STRENGTHS

- Small file size- efficient for web and access copies
- Universally supported across platforms and browsers
- Fast loading- ideal for public access and exhibits

LIMITATIONS

- Lossy compression- quality loss with repeated saves
- Not ideal as an archival master
- Sometimes used as preservation copy where storage is limited

JPEG LOSSY COMPRESSION

and cast in his lot with the emigrants, and would sail with the pioneers, gave confidence in the statements of the reverend gentleman, so that the seed fell into soil prepared and ready to receive it. At the end of the address I stepped forward and had a conversation with Mr. Burns, who, on returning to Edinburgh, communicated to the Secretary of the Otago Association, Mr. M'Glashan, the substance of that interview, and the result was an immediate offer of a free passage to the South of New Zealand, on condition of my remaining there for a limited time—five years.

TIFF

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JPEG

JPEG 2000

OVERVIEW

- .jp2 file extension
- Developed as a replacement for JPEG, but never widely adopted
- Used by some large universities and museums
- Supports lossy or lossless compression, depending on settings

STRENGTHS

- Smaller file sizes (similar to JPEG)
- Flexible compression options

LIMITATIONS

- Limited support across systems and software
- Often requires conversion to JPEG for access
- Longevity concerns if future systems don't support JP2
- Management complexity

PDFs

OVERVIEW

- PDF (Portable Document Format) developed by Adobe
- Common, widely supported document format
- PDF/A = archival version meeting ISO standards
 - Designed for longterm preservation
 - Self-contained: embeds all fonts, images, and components
 - Current standard: PDF/A4

KEY CHARACTERISTICS

- Multi-layer structure
- Versions of PDF/A:
 - A-1 – suitable for simple scanned docs
 - A-2 – adds layers, transparency, and embedding of other PDF/As
 - A-3 – allows non-PDF attachments
 - A-4 – adds JavaScript support
- PDF/A- Only slightly larger than standard PDFs
- ISO requires backward compatibility for future viewing

PDFs

STRENGTHS

- Universally supported across platforms and devices
- Multi-page, ideal for reports, books, theses
- Handles text + images well
- OCR capability (useful for digitised text)
- Can conform to PDF/UA for accessibility

LIMITATIONS

- Fonts must be embedded
- Difficult to extract or validate content
- Encryption not allowed for archival copies
- Metadata must follow standards
- OCR PDFs may not fully meet accessibility requirements

EPUBs

OVERVIEW

- Designed for eBooks
- Reflowable text adapts to screen size for better readability
- Built on HTML /CSS
- Supports accessibility features (text-to-speech, font resizing, screen readers)

STRENGTHS

- Highly accessible and user-friendly across devices
- Flexible layout and font customization
- Ideal for both born-digital and digitised texts
- Supports embedded metadata

LIMITATIONS

- Appearance can vary across platforms and devices
- Complex structure makes long-term preservation challenging
- Requires specialised tools and knowledge to create and maintain

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[BOOKS FOR SALE]

Publication details

Conditions of use

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NARRATIVE
OF A
VOYAGE
TO
NEW ZEALAND,

Performed in the years 1814 and 1815,
IN COMPANY WITH THE REV. SAMUEL MARSDEN,
Principal Chaplain of New South Wales.

BY
JOHN LIDDIARD NICHOLAS, ESQ.

FORMAT COMPARISON

TIFF	JPEG	JP2
Lossless compression	Lossy compression	Lossy or lossless
High quality & stable	Quality degrades with edits	Mid-quality with stable capability
Large file size	Smaller file size	Smaller file size
Not supported on all platforms	Widely supported	Not supported on all platforms
Preservation Master	Access Copy	Debatable

TIFF VS JPEG VS JP2

PDF	EPUB
Mixed (text + image)	Compressed (HTML/CSS)
Preserves Layout	Reflowable
Displays the same on any device	Rendering Inconsistencies
Widely supported	Not supported by all platforms
Proprietary features may hinder longevity	Preservation complexity
Accessibility features (OCR) but not ideal	Better for accessibility
Suitable for Access & Preservation	Access format, nonarchival

PDF VS EPUB

TIFF

Scanning rare books, manuscripts, archival photos and ephemera

JPEG

Web delivery of digitised images converted from TIFF

PDF

Dissertations, digitised books, searchable documents

EPUB

Converting digitised texts for e-readers and accessibility

USE CASES

TOOLS

OVERVIEW

- DROID (Digital Record Object Identification)
- DROID is an open source tool developed by The National Archives (UK).
- It is used to **automatically identify file formats** based on their internal signatures, not just file extensions.

PURPOSE

- To **identify and validate the true format** of digital files.
- To **detect unknown or obsolete formats** that may need migration.
- To support digital preservation planning by providing format risk information.
- To generate reports or inventories of files across a collection or repository.

DROID

DROID

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R
ID	PARENT_ID	URI	FILE_PATH	NAME	METHOD	STATUS	SIZE	TYPE	EXT	LAST_MODIFIED	EXTENSIO	HASH	FORMAT_C	UID	MIME_TY	FORMAT_NAME	FORMAT_VE
2		file:/C:/Us	C:\Users\s	bee1003		Done		Folder		2024-07-08	FALSE						
3	2	file:/C:/Us	C:\Users\s	64.jpg	Signature	Done	140591	File	jpg	2011-08-04	FALSE		1	fmt/44	image/jpe	JPEG File Interchange Format	1.02
4	2	file:/C:/Us	C:\Users\s	65.jpg	Signature	Done	134669	File	jpg	2011-08-04	FALSE		1	fmt/44	image/jpe	JPEG File Interchange Format	1.02
5	2	file:/C:/Us	C:\Users\s	66.jpg	Signature	Done	135485	File	jpg	2011-08-04	FALSE		1	fmt/44	image/jpe	JPEG File Interchange Format	1.02
6	2	file:/C:/Us	C:\Users\s	67.jpg	Signature	Done	162882	File	jpg	2011-08-04	FALSE		1	fmt/44	image/jpe	JPEG File Interchange Format	1.02
7	2	file:/C:/Us	C:\Users\s	68.jpg	Signature	Done	156388	File	jpg	2011-08-04	FALSE		1	fmt/44	image/jpe	JPEG File Interchange Format	1.02
8	2	file:/C:/Us	C:\Users\s	69.jpg	Signature	Done	160588	File	jpg	2011-08-04	FALSE		1	fmt/44	image/jpe	JPEG File Interchange Format	1.02
9	2	file:/C:/Us	C:\Users\s	70.jpg	Signature	Done	150351	File	jpg	2011-08-04	FALSE		1	fmt/44	image/jpe	JPEG File Interchange Format	1.02
10	2	file:/C:/Us	C:\Users\s	71.jpg	Signature	Done	158195	File	jpg	2011-08-04	FALSE		1	fmt/44	image/jpe	JPEG File Interchange Format	1.02
11	2	file:/C:/Us	C:\Users\s	72.jpg	Signature	Done	157100	File	jpg	2011-08-04	FALSE		1	fmt/44	image/jpe	JPEG File Interchange Format	1.02
12	2	file:/C:/Us	C:\Users\s	73.jpg	Signature	Done	158509	File	jpg	2011-08-04	FALSE		1	fmt/44	image/jpe	JPEG File Interchange Format	1.02
13	2	file:/C:/Us	C:\Users\s	74.jpg	Signature	Done	132391	File	jpg	2011-08-04	FALSE		1	fmt/44	image/jpe	JPEG File Interchange Format	1.02
14	2	file:/C:/Us	C:\Users\s	75.jpg	Signature	Done	38999	File	jpg	2011-08-04	FALSE		1	fmt/44	image/jpe	JPEG File Interchange Format	1.02

DROID

DROID

OVERVIEW

- PRONOMs a technical registry developed and maintained by The National Archives (UK).
- It provides detailed, authoritative information about file formats, software, and format versions used in digital preservation.
- PRONOM is publicly accessible online and is regularly updated through community contributions.

PURPOSE

- To identify, describe, and manage file formats within digital collections.
- To support digital preservation planning by helping determine which formats are stable or at risk.

PRONOM

PRONOM

OVERVIEW

- Adobe Acrobat is **widely used software** suite developed by Adobe Systems for creating, viewing, and managing PDF (Portable Document Format) files.
- In digital preservation, it's primarily used to **create, edit, validate, and convert documents** into preservation-friendly formats such as PDF/A or simply PDF.

PURPOSE

- **Convert image files** (TIFFs, JPEGs, PNGs) into PDFs or PDF/A archival files.
- **Apply Optical Character Recognition (OCR)** to scanned images for text search and accessibility.
- **Combine multiple images or pages** into a single, multi-page PDF document.
- **Annotate or digitally sign** documents to preserve authenticity.

ADOBE ACROBAT

Share

Send for comments

Protect a PDF

Edit a PDF

Create a PDF

Combine files

Fill & Sign

Organize pages

See all tools ...

Quick

Create a PDF from any format

Single file

Multiple files

Scanner

Web page

Clipboard

Blank page

Select a file

Choose from docx, xlsx, txt, etc.

[Check more formats](#)

Advanced settings

Create

[Help](#)

ADOBE ACROBAT

ADOBE ACROBAT

ADOBE ACROBAT

- ImageMagick- File format migration
- Free Commander- File management tool
- Tools Grid- https://coptr.digipres.org/Tools_Grid
- Digital Preservation Handbook <https://www.dpconline.org/handbook/technical-solutions-and-tools/tools>
- Adobe Bridge- <https://www.adobe.com/products/bridge.html> Free digital asset management app (good for combining many images into PDF)
- PDFgear <http://pdfgear.com/> - Free PDF editor- merge, convert, split,

TOOLS/RESOURCES

🏠 COLLECTIONS /

Early New Zealand Books

The ENZB database has the full text of over 500 books about New Zealand from 1642 to around 1870 including subsequently published diaries and letters from the period.

ENZB JOURNEY

- Public access to Early New Zealand Books was lost due to cyber attacks
- The old platform hosted mostly EPUB files, as well as some PDFs
- EPUB and PDF files are supported on AlmaD, the new platform
- Existing catalogue records
- We had access to TIFF and JPEG files from the original digitisation project

PROJECT OVERVIEW

- EPUB files don't display correctly in the third-party file viewer (Primo)
- The team decided to only upload PDFs
- Not all resources had PDF files, but we were able to find TIFF or JPEG
- Converted TIFF or JPEG to PDF

CHALLENGES

- Saving PDFs as PDF/A better for archival
- Sometimes it is necessary to focus on access when under time constraints
- Documentation is crucial (provenance, copyright permissions, project history)

LESSONS LEARNT

QUIZ

SUMMARY

- File formats shape how we **preserve and access** digital content.
- Choose **sustainable, open/supported, well-documented formats** where possible.
- Use **lossless formats** (e.g. TIFF, PDF/A) for preservation; **lossy** ones (e.g. JPEG) for access.
- Regularly assess **obsolescence risks** and plan for **migration**.
Tools like **DROID** and **PRONOM** help identify and manage formats.
- Balance **preservation integrity** with **usability and accessibility**.
- Document your choices — **why** and **how** you manage file formats.

**“GOOD FORMAT CHOICES TODAY
MAKE PRESERVATION EASIER
TOMORROW.”**

REFERENCES

1. Library of Congress <https://loc.gov/preservation/resources/rfs/format-pref-summary.html>
2. <https://www.dpconline.org/>
3. <https://australasiapreserves.blogspot.com/p/digital-preservation-essentials.html>
4. <https://www.naa.gov.au/about-us/who-we-are/accountability-and-reporting/archival-policy-and-planning/preservation-digitalisation-standards>
5. <https://www.revolutiondatasystems.com/blog/the-importance-of-digital-preservation-file-formats-and-open-data-standards>
6. <https://www.infobelpro.com/en/blog/what-is-data-obsolescence>
7. <https://www.adobe.com/uk/acrobat/resources/document-files/pdf-types/pdf-a.html>
8. <https://library.unimelb.edu.au/digital-scholarship/digital-preservation/digital-preservation-guides/>

ANY QUESTIONS?

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